

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE REFORMS CARRIED OUT IN UZBEKISTAN TO REDUCE THE SHARE OF THE HIDDEN ECONOMY AND THE MECHANISMS USED IN THIS DIRECTION IN FOREIGN COUNTRIES

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Annatation: The article states that today a number of changes are being made in the tax sector in our country, and therefore several innovations are being developed in the tax system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. However, since studies and research on these changes have not been conducted, the need for studies on the adopted decisions and innovations increases. This article analyzes the work carried out in foreign countries to reduce the shadow economy, the changes made in the tax sector and their effectiveness, reveals the content of innovations in the tax system in our country, and formulates conclusions within the framework of the topic.

Keywords: tax system, tax reform, tax incentives, tax control, tax burden, digital economy, fiscal efficiency, digital payment

The increasing processes of globalization, digital transformation and economic instability in the world economy are forcing states to reconsider their tax policies. The increasing processes of globalization, digital transformation and economic instability in the world economy are forcing states to reconsider their tax policies. In such conditions, the tax system is manifested not only as a mechanism that forms the income of the state budget, but also as an important instrument for ensuring macroeconomic stability, stimulating investment activity and supporting socio-economic development. Therefore, the issue of transforming the tax system in accordance with the requirements of the Times is becoming a priority for the Republic of Uzbekistan, among many countries.

In recent years, as part of the large-scale economic reforms being implemented in Uzbekistan, special attention has been paid to the modernization of the tax sector. In particular, the innovations adopted in the tax sector in 2026 are significant in that they are aimed at bringing relations between the state and taxpayers to a qualitatively new level. These reforms are aimed at optimizing the tax burden, simplifying tax administration, widely introducing digital technologies, and strengthening voluntary tax compliance.

As part of the tax innovations introduced in 2026, measures such as digitization of tax administration, expansion of cashless settlements, strengthening transparent control mechanisms for large transactions, and revision of tax incentives were implemented. These changes, along with expanding the tax base, serve to reduce the share of the shadow economy and ensure the stability of tax revenues.

The study examined the reforms implemented in foreign countries to reduce the shadow economy and transition to a cashless system, as well as several changes made to the tax system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Based on the decisions taken on these innovations, regulatory documents and their theoretical foundations were studied.

Sweden, one of the most developed countries in the world, is considered the first country in the world to have almost completely switched to a cashless economy. In 1959, Swedish banks introduced the first plastic credit cards. In the 1980s and 1990s, automated teller machines (ATMs) and electronic payment systems began to spread widely. During this period, a large part of the population learned to pay through banks - this started much earlier than in other European countries. In 2009, the Swedish Central Bank (Riksbank) officially launched a “strategy for the transition to a cashless economy”. In 2018, the Swedish Parliament (Riksdag) adopted the “Cashless Economy Management Act”[1].

The Kenyan government has launched the eCitizen platform for all government services - all payments will be made online. The move is aimed at reducing cash in government payments, tax collection, transport and utilities. Today, 97% of financial transactions in the Kenyan economy are carried out digitally.

India has one of the largest digital payments infrastructures in the world, but the transition to this system has been gradual. In the 1990s, India began to modernize its banking system. In the 2000s, debit and credit cards, and later mobile banking, became popular. However, at that time, 90% of the population still used cash. In 2010, cashless payments accounted for only 3–5% of total transactions[2].

The transition to a non-cash (electronic payment) system in Uzbekistan has been gradual and long-term. It was formed through the process of introducing a progressive electronic payment system that began in the 1990s.

Table 1.

Indicators of cashless monetary systems in foreign countries

№	Country	The emergence of the Electron monetary system, the year	Introduction of electronic tourism by the Central Bank of states, Year	In the current period, the share of cash turnover by GDP (%)	In the current period, the share of cashless cash turnover by GDP (%)	All industry services share cashless cash receipts (%) at
1	Sweden	1950-1990	2009	1,5	98,5	90
2	Kenya	2003-2006	2007	3	97	97
3	India	1990-2010	1999	10	90	75
4	Nidirland	1990-2000	1995	5	95	85
5	Uzbekistan	1995-1996	1996	20	80	70

The Swedish model is characterized by a high level of digital literacy of the financial sector and a reliable banking system. This system is formed by a combination of a high level of social trust, legal stability and technological innovation. As a result, payments are made digitally in almost all sectors of the country's economy. Today, the share of cash turnover in GDP is 1.5%, while non-cash payments are 98.5%.

Today, the share of non-cash payments in the Kenyan economy is 97%, and cash is around 3%. Mobile applications became widespread in 2010–2015, and financial inclusion of the population (integration into the banking system) increased significantly. In the case of Kenya, we can observe the “leapfrogging effect”, that is, the process of developing countries bypassing the traditional banking system and switching directly to mobile finance. This situation shows that, despite the low financial infrastructure, innovative technologies have increased economic integration[3].

The Indian government initiated the introduction of electronic funds transfer (EFT) and card payments in the 1990s–2010s. The demonetization policy of 2016 (the withdrawal of 500 and 1000 rupee notes from circulation) initiated a sharp shift towards a cashless economy. This was followed by the launch of the Unified Payments Interface (UPI) system and the widespread use of mobile applications (Paytm, BHIM, Google Pay). Today, cash turnover accounts for 10% of GDP, while non-cash payments account for 90%[4].

The Netherlands introduced electronic payments through the Chipknip and PIN systems in the 1990s and 2000s. In 1995, a national electronic payment system was created through the Interpay platform. In the 2000s, card payments began to dominate all major retail chains. Today, cash turnover accounts for 5% of GDP, while the share of non-cash payments exceeds 95%. In the case of the Netherlands, regulatory stability, EU standards and technological innovation work in harmony. This system is characterized by inclusive finance, a secure payment architecture and international interoperability.

The emerging digital payment system was launched in 1995–1996 by the Central Bank of Uzbekistan, which introduced an interbank electronic payment system. In 1996, a fully electronic settlement system was launched. In 2015–2018, national mobile applications such as Uzcard, Humo, Apelsin, Payme, and Click appeared. In 2019, the Law “On Payments and Payment Systems” was adopted, legally strengthening payment services. Today, the share of cash in GDP is 20%, and the share of non-cash payments is 80%. The share of non-cash payments in all service sectors has reached 70%[5].

In accordance with the tax reforms currently underway, several decisions and innovations have been adopted in the Republic of Uzbekistan. In this regard, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 10.12.2025, Law No. PF-246, was developed on additional measures aimed at popularizing non-cash payments and reducing the share of the shadow economy.

Starting from April 1, 2026, payments for the following will be made only through bank cards or electronic payment systems:

- (a) services provided by state bodies;
- (b) payments for the use of electricity, natural gas, drinking water (excluding payments made through bank cash desks);
- (v) alcohol and tobacco products;
- (g) sales of oil and gas products to the population through fuel stations for vehicles and services for charging electric vehicles;
- (d) goods and services worth more than 25 million soums (excluding agricultural products);
- (j) sale and purchase of real estate, vehicles of categories M, N, O and G, not more than ten years old, and special vehicles. In this case:
 - (i) settlements between the seller and the buyer under purchase and sale contracts are carried out through the exchange of information between the information systems of banks and notary bodies (excluding payments made through bank cash desks);
 - (ii) the basis for notarial execution of contracts is information confirming the payment by means of electronic information exchange by commercial banks and payment organizations.

3.The following:

- (a) The Central Bank shall introduce a single QR code for accepting electronic payments by all legal entities engaged in trade and service provision by January 1, 2026;
- (b) The Tax Committee, together with the Central Bank, shall take measures to establish the acceptance of electronic payments by all legal entities engaged in trade and service provision by a single QR code generated in banks from January 1, 2026. In this regard, from July 1, 2026:
 - (i) all legal entities in the trade and service sector are also required to accept payments through a unified QR code payment system;
 - (ii) failure to use unified QR codes is considered a violation of trade rules[6].

The reforms carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan to modernize the economy, digitalize tax administration and ensure fiscal transparency are yielding significant positive results in reducing the share of the shadow economy. The financial digital transformation carried out in the country in recent years, in particular the widespread introduction of cashless payment systems, along with the transparency of state fiscal policy, are helping to reduce the size of the shadow economy.

As a result of the study, the high share of cash circulation in Uzbekistan has long narrowed the tax base and hindered the full formation of state budget revenues. Therefore, the widespread introduction of cashless payments, the development of electronic payment infrastructure and the integration of digital financial technologies have emerged as an effective mechanism for systematically combating the main structural causes of the shadow economy.

In general, the introduction of digital finance and a cashless payment system in the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the systemic reforms that will lead to a reduction in the shadow economy, strengthening tax discipline, increasing economic transparency, and improving the investment climate.

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